

Effectiveness of Eye Shields During Kendo Strikes

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Abstract: This study evaluated the effectiveness of face shields in protecting the eyes from splinters generated during standard kendo head strikes. A shinai was coated with red paint to simulate splinter dispersion and used to strike a kendo dummy. Results showed that the dummy equipped with a face shield exhibited no paint marks in the eye region, indicating effective protection. In contrast, the dummy without a face shield sustained direct impact to the left eye area. These findings demonstrate that face shields provide effective protection against potential eye injuries during kendo practice.

Keywords: — Kendo, eye injury, sports injury, eye protection, safety.

I. INTRODUCTION

Eye protective equipment is common in many sports and industries, such as recreational biking and woodworking. Helmets are standard, but protective eyewear is increasingly used to prevent injuries from small projectiles, such as high-speed pebble ricochets or wood chips during cutting [1,2]. Similarly, the sport of kendo (Japanese fencing) utilizes head and eye protective gear. Instead of helmets, kendo practitioners wear a face/headgear called men [3]. The use of men has been shown to reduce the risk of concussion [4]. Recently, eye shields were introduced as part of recommended guidelines for kendo federations during the COVID-19 pandemic to prevent infection [5,6]. However, paralleling the relaxation of mask mandates worldwide, eye shield use has declined. As of April 1, 2023, the All United States Kendo Federation (AUSKF) no longer mandates masks or shields in practice or competition [7]. Consequently, eye shield usage in kendo is no longer prevalent, even in high-level matches such as national tournaments (see Figure 1).

Kendo-related eye injuries are rare but can be serious or even life-threatening [8]. In Japan, cases have been reported of middle and high school kendo

practitioners sustaining eye injuries from shinai splinters penetrating the men through narrow gaps, causing traumatic optic neuropathy and, in one case, death due to subarachnoid hemorrhage [9]. Some injuries may be less obvious, as in the case of one practitioner who described the following:

"Several days after training, my eye became very itchy and bloodshot. It didn't hurt, but I couldn't stop rubbing it because of some foreign irritant. Initially, I thought I had a sty, but eye drops did not help. An optometrist identified and removed a tiny speck under a slit lamp biomicroscope, which appeared to be bamboo fiber. I was lucky that my eyeball was not scratched severely." [10]

Following such incidents, the kendo community, including the All Japan Kendo Federation, has emphasized proper shinai maintenance to prevent splinter injuries [11], but the use of eye shields has not been widely promoted. Although eye and face shields are commercially available (see Figure 2), recent high-level global kendo tournament photos from Milano (19th world kendo tournament, July 4-7, 2024 Milano) show that none of the world class athletes from 61 countries wore eye protection [12].

This observation raises questions about the effectiveness of face shields in protecting the eyes from splinters generated during standard kendo head strikes.

Fig. 1 19th world kendo championship, July 2024, Milano [12].

Fig. 2 “Eye Guard” (left) and “Face Shield” (right) [13].

II. METHODS

A 170 cm tall training dummy/mannequin with a drawn face and fully equipped with bogu was subjected to 40 vertical men strikes using a shinai coated with red paint to simulate splinter dispersion. The first 20 strikes were delivered with an eye shield (experimental condition), and the next 20 strikes without an eye shield (control). Effectiveness was evaluated by the presence or absence, and the dot count of paint marks on the drawn eye region.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 3 Mannequin with Eye Shield after 20 vertical strikes. Has no paint mark (0 dot count) directly on the eyes .

Fig. 4 Close Mannequin without Eye Shield after 20 vertical strikes. Has paint marks (3 dots count) on the left eye.

The dummy equipped with a face shield exhibited no paint marks in the eye region, indicating effective protection (see Figure 3).

Conversely, the dummy without a face shield sustained direct impact to the left eye area with 3 dots count (1 on the right), confirming vulnerability to splinter penetration without protective gear (see Figure 4).

IV. DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the effectiveness of face shields in protecting the eyes from splinters generated during standard kendo head strikes. A shinai was coated with red paint to simulate splinter dispersion and used to strike a kendo dummy. When the shinai strikes a headgear and breaks, the impact generates splinters that follow specific trajectories. The paint dispersion pattern on the headgear mimics the splinter trajectories, spreading outward along similar paths. Thus, the paint patterns can serve as a visual proxy for the physical splinter paths, illustrating how fragments might disperse during a break. Results showed that the dummy equipped with a face shield protected the eye region, whereas the dummy without a face shield did not. These findings demonstrate that face shields provide effective protection against potential eye injuries during kendo practice.

This study has several limitations. First, red paint was used to simulate splinter dispersion instead of actual splinters. Paint particles are more likely to detach from the shinai and transfer through the men and into the eye shield (or eye) than splinters. Paint also has less momentum compared to splinters, which may affect impact probability. The viscosity, surface adhesion, and fragility of the paint can affect how well it mimics actual splinters. If the paint disperses too broadly or too little, it may not accurately reflect the true splinter trajectory. Future research could use eye shields and dummies with adhesive surfaces to more accurately replicate splinter impacts.

Second, the experiment involved only 40 strikes on a stationary dummy for each condition. Repeated strikes on a moving or shaking dummy may affect the position or integrity of the eye shield, potentially increasing eye injury risk.

Third, the mannequin lacked three-dimensional, anatomically accurate facial features such as realistic eyes, nose, and mouth, which may affect generalizability. Future studies should use more lifelike mannequins.

Finally, data were collected in a controlled environment with vertical men strikes only (i.e. no side strikes). Actual kendo matches in tournaments involve diverse strike types and dynamic movement. Practitioners may inevitably bump into each other's men headgear, which

may shift the eye shield and affect eye shield efficacy. Field data would provide valuable additional insights and future studies could include athletes using painted shinai while equipped with swim goggles to determine the efficacy of face shields.

V. CONCLUSION

Eye shields are effective in protecting the eyes from shinai splinters, yet their use has declined since the pandemic. Just as in clinical oncology, where targeted preventive strategies have proven effective in reducing treatment complications [14], preventive strategies in sports, such as the adoption of eye shields, offer a proactive approach in safeguarding athletes' health. Like other sports that mandate eye protection, kendo practitioners should be encouraged to use eye shields along with men. Challenges remain in convincing practitioners to adopt shields, possibly due to concerns about visual limitations, comfort, or fit—especially across different facial anatomies. Future studies should include field data with dynamic or tournament based evaluations, and investigate barriers to eye shield usage in the kendo community.

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